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Correction: Indolizine quaternary ammonium salt inhibitors part II: a reinvestigation of an old-fashioned strong acid corrosion inhibitor phenacyl quinolinium bromide and its indolizine derivative

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Correction for 'Indolizine quaternary ammonium salt inhibitors part II: a reinvestigation of an old-fashioned strong acid corrosion inhibitor phenacyl quinolinium bromide and its indolizine derivative' by Yefei Wang *et al.*, *New J. Chem.*, 2018, **42**, 12977–12989.

Due to a clerical error, the labeling of the atoms in Fig. 1–3 is incorrect in the published article. The correct figures are shown below.

Fig. 1 Structure of indolizine and the formation of BQD from BQC.

Fig. 2 Synthesis of phenacyl quinolinium bromide (PaQBr) and its dimer derivative, DiPaQBr.

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Fig. 3 The formation mechanism of DiPaQBr from PaQBr.

The Royal Society of Chemistry apologises for these errors and any consequent inconvenience to authors and readers.

